

Call for Participation

Good morning/afternoon <name>,

We are a group of researchers at New York University and Cornell University and we are conducting research into how online platforms can better support micro- and small- business owners in navigating technology-enabled attacks on their person, their family, or their business.

I would like to invite you to participate in a ~75 minute interview to learn more about your enterprise or business.

I would like to hear your experiences in the challenges you might have experienced (e.g., with suppliers, business partners, or customers), how you might have navigated them, and how platforms can do more to help. Challenges might include 'problem customers' leaving fraudulent reviews on products or services that you provide, sending unwelcome emails to your business via direct or open emails, or reporting your business to the platform you may use for hosting. **Something specific to the organization we're inviting.**

The interview shall be conducted over Zoom for no more than 75 minutes, and I would not ask you to share any personal or identifiable details of any of your customers or clients. If you are interested in participating in this study, please fill out your availability to interview on [Calendly](#).

Our research has gone on to inform the safer re-design of consumer based products, online policies, and even legislation to ensure that technologies are safer for all. We would be happy to provide more information about our investigation and share the results of our study to assist you in your work.

We really appreciate your time and consideration.

All the best,

Arkabrabha Bhattacharya, Nazanin Sabri, Sterling Williams-Ceci, and Rosanna Bellini

Population-Specific.

Population 1: Survivors of Intimate Partner Violence

Good morning/afternoon <name>,

We are a group of researchers at New York University and Cornell University investigating the use of finances to cause harm between people that are, or have been, in a relationship with each other. This might be called 'financial deception' or 'financial abuse' and might include a range of different behaviors

where a person controls the other's ability to acquire, use and maintain financial resources (e.g. bank accounts, cash, employment). **Something specific to the organization we're inviting.**

Given your expertise in this area, I was hoping you might have time to meet with me via Zoom for ~75 minutes? I would not ask you to share any personal or identifiable details of any of your customers or clients, as we would only be interested in talking about the general services available to cases such as these. It would really help to inform our understanding as to how we can encourage platforms to provide tailored policies and platform-specific tools to help small business owners navigate these challenges. We would be happy to provide more information about our investigation and share the results of our study to assist you in your work.

If you are interested in participating in this study, please fill out your availability to interview on [Calendly](#).

We really appreciate your time and consideration.

All the best,

Arkaprabha Bhattacharya, Nazanin Sabri, Sterling Williams-Ceci, and Rosanna Bellini

Population 2: Black and Minority Ethnic Groups

Good morning/afternoon **<name>**,

We are a group of researchers at New York University and Cornell University investigating the financial impact of so-called 'problem customers' for small business owners who have used targeted attacks that may be motivated by hate, harassment or harm. These attacks might include leaving fraudulent reviews on products or services that you provide, sending unwelcome emails to your business via direct or open emails, and reporting your business to the platform you may use for hosting. **Something specific to the organization we're inviting.**

Given your expertise in this area, I was hoping you might have time to meet with me via Zoom for ~60 minutes? I would not ask you to share any personal or identifiable details of any of your customers or clients, as we would only be interested in talking about the general services available to cases such as these. It would really help to inform our understanding as to how we can encourage platforms to provide tailored policies and platform-specific tools to help small business owners navigate these challenges. We would be happy to provide more information about our investigation and share the results of our study to assist you in your work.

We really appreciate your time and consideration.

All the best,

Arkaprabha Bhattacharya, Sterling Williams-Ceci, and Rosanna Bellini

Population 3: Persons Involved in Political Campaigns

Good morning/afternoon <name>,

We are a group of researchers at New York University and Cornell University investigating the financial impact of so-called ‘problem customers’ for small business owners who have politically-oriented products or services that may be motivated by hate, harassment or harm. These attacks might include leaving fraudulent reviews on products or services that you provide, sending unwelcome emails to your business via direct or open emails, and reporting your business to the platform you may use for hosting. **Something specific to the organization we’re inviting.**

Given your expertise in this area, I was hoping you might have time to meet with me via Zoom for ~75 minutes? I would not ask you to share any personal or identifiable details of any of your customers or clients, as we would only be interested in talking about the general services available to cases such as these. It would really help to inform our understanding as to how we can encourage platforms to provide tailored policies and platform-specific tools to help small business owners navigate these challenges. We would be happy to provide more information about our investigation and share the results of our study to assist you in your work.

If you are interested in participating in this study, please fill out your availability to interview on [Calendly](#).

We really appreciate your time and consideration.

All the best,

Arkaprabha Bhattacharya, Sterling Williams-Ceci, and Rosanna Bellini
